

The Role of Television in the Global News Media System. This is the First Time in the History of Television in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article talks about ways to involve young people in sports and further develop their technical and tactical skills.

Keywords: modes of action, stages of development, problem solution, technical and tactical solutions.

Television services have a special place in the content of our past days. The city of Tashkent is the capital of our state and the place where the best TV shows are broadcast. The first black-and-white-colored TV studios were established in 1925 in the city of Tashkent on the grounds of Belyansky and Grobovsky. This invention, which is subject to the will of the world, is certainly a great pride for us to present in our Fatherland. The first television production in 1928 showed the objects. In 1956, he became the first person in the Asian continent to be recognized in Tashkent by a television in black and white. Since then, over the past half-century, television has made significant progress in terms of quality. The appearance of modern televisions, which are attenuated from the right side, can be the reason for the delay in transmitting television signals. The victory in Uzbekistan is considered one of the reforms implemented under the leadership of our President in the years of independence to promote the best news media, television and radio stations. Modern television equipment and advanced media techniques are widely used in the preparation and distribution of TV shows. Digital TV is different from conventional TV, where the viewer is calm, the colors are bright, and every detail is clear. Uzbekistan became one of the first countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States to switch to digital television and has supported digital television in the republic since 2007. Tashkent and Bukhara launched a step-by-step approach to digital terrestrial television broadcasts in the experimental zone. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of April 17, 2012 on the State Program on Digital Television in the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the technical and technological transition has served as the legal basis for this. It is noteworthy that the program provides for the development of modern equipment for the reception of digital television signals in our country, as well as the provision of care to the population. Particular attention was paid to the preparation of the social package for the use of digital television, the development of the technical possibilities for the transmission of television and radio archival materials in digital format. The social package of digital television is the package of television channels that receive payment from the operators and providers for the distribution of social media. We can say that this is one of the most important aspects of the development of human resources in our country.

Therefore, in the process of diversification of digital TV channels, special attention has been paid to enriching the social package of digital TV. In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on increasing the capabilities of digital television

channels of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan, using them in full format, achieving their quality standards and providing services, adopted on July 30, 2012, new digital television channels around the world have been expanded. In the country, the numbered television channel “Balazhan” with measured children’s shoes was launched by the closed joint stock company “Zhaslar” TV and radio channel. Within the framework of the implementation of the State Program of Technical and Technological Transition to Digital Television, the Company “UZDIGITAL TV” was established with the assistance of the State Authority for Communications, Informatization and Telecommunication Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and today it is one of the leading operators in the country providing digital television services to legal and physical persons. As a result of the received proposals, significant results were achieved in the introduction of digital television programs in the short term. European standard for digital terrestrial television adopted in Uzbekistan. One of its main advantages is to be able to receive a signal accurately and not to receive other signals that return it. Today, 45 percent of the territory of our state is covered by digital television. A large number of percussion instruments have been installed in Tashkent, Andijan, Bukhara, Gulistan, Karshi, Kokan, Samarkand, Navoi, Nokis and Urgenish. In some provinces and cities, TV programs will be regularly broadcast in digital format during 2012. By the end of 2017, all regions of Kazakhstan will fully switch to digital television. As a result of the implementation of the new format of broadcasting in Uzbekistan in 2011, the country’s national television - HDTV, which is the first among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, will be able to broadcast in high quality. A new way of broadcasting television in the world is created by HDTV, which gives the opportunity to watch movies with a quiet television program. The first HD channel to be broadcast in Kazakhstan. “UZHD” is one of those channels. State unitary enterprise “Uzbekistan MTRK” media center organized by the press of the President of Uzbekistan will be considered as the technological basis for the long-term development of telecasts on the air, which are largely silent. Well-known Russian television personality V. Posner praised the victory of the television channels among the media: "Television and cinema have a great impact on the perception of the whole society." [1]. In accordance with the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on increasing the number of digital television channels of the Uzbekistan Television and Radio Company, the right to use them in the full format, to preserve the rich historical and spiritual heritage of our country, and to promote it to the world, new media and educational channels around the world will be launched on December 31, 2012.

In view of this, it is necessary to inform the public about the important moments in the scientific and cultural life of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are derived from the possibilities of various modern interactive forms of broadcasting, digital and multimedia technology, and educational television channels. It also presents the best examples of music, theater and visual arts, produces television programs on national literature and biographies of our famous artists. TV channel "Worldwide" will provide the people of Uzbekistan with a comprehensive tourist information about the history of Uzbekistan, the development of ecological and educational tourism in the country. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan expressed his gratitude to the efforts of our country to spread the information about the Republic of Uzbekistan through the production of high-level artistic, scientific-publicist and educational programs and broadcasting them not only on its own channels, but also on the TV channels of the world countries. To create high-quality television and radio broadcasts using high-tech equipment and radio and television technology in the most modern media technologies available, as well as to prepare millions of television technicians and editors in this direction and to fully implement the system of retraining in the Tashkent University of Information Technologies “Television Technologies Faculty”. The opening of the Republican College of Television and Radio Arts in our region will help to reach the younger generations. This enables users of modern digital television to model the viewing process of television shows. The above-mentioned state program was created in order to provide new types of services. For example, the EPS has been re-elected. This electronic TV program

will help you to find out what is shown on each channel and when the film is broadcast. Users can indicate that the content is being broadcast, view the distribution of films, add or remove subtitles, select the language of the audio, set the memory, and many other functions. The selected display may also have a tracking function that prevents the player from watching a football game if the film is damaged. This function will appear on the screen a few minutes before the start of the selected show, even if the TV is on a different channel. In the service of EPG, there is also a function of “Parental control “of the transmission of the digital signal of the channels where children can watch .. Other channels will be closed for viewing as a result of parental permission and password. Uzbekistan’s television industry is proving that the country is completely detached from its rich history. This means that in the near future, thanks to the sustainable implementation of the adopted State programs, every citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be able to use high-quality television services ..

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